

VALKYRIES

D3.8. Report on the technical, legal and ethical profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities M24

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1. Executive Summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to study, compare and develop the technical, legal and ethical issues related to the interoperability of first responders and other relevant actors in emergency situations. A variety of studies and trials on the subject as well as existing public and private initiatives have been analysed. The developments are currently most clearly seen in the eHealth sector, but we believe that many of the principles and steps followed can be applicable to emergency situations. To the challenges and opportunities found in all of them, we have added our own suggestions, which will be further developed and refined as the project progresses and lessons are learned. In order for the study to be realistic and applicable, it is of great importance to closely monitor the results of the Use Cases as well as the other research tasks, as valuable facts will emerge and the solution will be based on experience. Always with the aim of providing an innovative solution that is aware of reality, takes advantage of existing technologies and complies with EU regulations on the subject.

This document constitutes the updated version of the D3.2 and D3.7. The new content with respect them has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

2. Identification

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3. Background

The ever-growing human, economic and environmental losses due to natural and/or man-made disasters demand a systematic, holistic, inter-governmental and multi-disciplinary approach to the management of large-scale crisis. However, crisis management is usually coordinated by local authorities, supported by a variety of different national and international crisis management organizations, all acting relatively autonomously. Coordination actions usually adopt non-interoperable information management tools, due to the heterogeneity of the involved organizations, limiting or even hindering the coordination efforts (Cinque, 2015).

Without a reliable way to communicate with the field, incident commanders lack the necessary situational awareness to ensure an appropriate response to the situations they are routinely called on to manage (Guddemi, 2021). First responders depend on a seamless flow of voice, video, and data communications to guide their response whether it be a small-scale incident, a significant natural or manmade disaster, or a pre-planned event where tens of thousands of people will be present. Emergency response officials must be able to communicate quickly and easily to fully coordinate their preparedness and response in these situations.

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments. For the set harmonisation purposes, the project will consider the current and detected issues concerning ethics, regulation, certification, accreditation, agreements of conformity criteria, and all the standardisation stages. The resulting discoveries, methodologies, strategies, and support to harmonisation tactics/tools shall be enforced and demonstrated on a reference integrated platform driven by real needs focused on closing the disruption gap. It must also be noted that, for answering the much-needed coordination of civil and military cooperation in responding to mass disasters with a large number of victims, and for taking into account the different normative and ethical landscape among participating countries with reference to the role of military services in such mass disasters instances, Valkyries involves partners with expertise or relationships in the military domain.

For these reasons and more, the aim of this deliverable is to contribute to the improvement of interoperability by capturing the opportunities and challenges of the different ethical, legal and technical profiles surrounding the solution developed by VALKYRIES. Studying the existing features but especially looking for improvements for the less developed parts. The deliverable will focus on the three categories presented but will also discuss others that are of great interest and broad importance in order to understand the whole scheme of needs. Some of the issues that will be analysed are of semantic, syntactic, organisational and budgetary nature, among others.

3.1. Defining interoperability

Before starting to develop the topic, it is useful to describe what interoperability means and what its benefits, challenges and drivers are. Its application is common to most sectors and levels of society as it is of tremendous importance to boost synergies, facilitate communication, reduce costs and offer a more successful solution, among other aspects. In this sense, the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) understands interoperability as the *“ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems”*. A definition more oriented to the health sector,

where VALKYRIES is active, could be *"the ability, facilitated by ICT applications and systems, to exchange, understand and act on citizens/patients and other health-related information and knowledge; among linguistically and culturally disparate health professionals, patients and other actors and organisations; within and across health system jurisdictions in a collaborative manner."* (HITCH-D6, 2011).

Basically, as the Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS) states, it is the capability of different information systems, devices and applications (systems) to access, exchange, integrate and cooperatively use data in a coordinated manner, within and across organizational, regional and national boundaries, to provide timely and seamless portability of information and optimize the health of individuals and populations globally. Within emergency management, it concerns in particular the ability of emergency response officials to share information via voice and data signals on demand, in real time, when needed, and as authorized. Making it possible for emergency response agencies responding to catastrophic accidents or disasters to work effectively together.

The European Commission identified the need for interoperability between public administrations back in 1994 and since then, it has supported programmes to develop, promote and use interoperability solutions in the EU. In 2010 it adopted COM(2010) 744 final, entitled *"Towards interoperability for European public services"* containing in annex the European interoperability strategy (EIS) and the European interoperability framework (EIF). Since then, the European interoperability framework has served as a reference throughout the Union and beyond, and it was the basis of most national interoperability frameworks (NIFs) and strategies. Building on this success, it is now time to update and extend the current European interoperability framework to take on board new or revised interoperability requirements that arise from Union policies and programmes as well as from public administrations, while taking into account technological developments and trends.

The Interoperability Solutions for European Public Administrations (ISA) programme (2010-2015), and its successor the ISA² programme (2016-2020), are the main instruments through which the current European interoperability strategy and European interoperability framework have been implemented. This has involved a variety of actions that aimed to improve digital collaboration between public administrations in Europe.

The interest in this area is clear and it is represented in the various initiatives promoted by the European Union, its member countries and other actors in the international community. Many are making individual and collective efforts to improve health care, to do so in a more integrated and efficient way, taking into account everyone and respecting the different regulatory frameworks. It is also a reality that we live in a digitised society that every day sees technological improvements and opportunities which, if well exploited, can contribute enormously to the creation of modern solutions.

3.2. Main challenges

- **Disjointed coordination**
Improving interoperability requires strong coordination between different organizations, regulators and leaders, as well as coordination within organizations. Regulators provide standards and rules for healthcare organizations to follow but organizations that want to be proactive about interoperability should consider creating a dedicated interoperability strategy and make interoperability planning a priority.
- **Lack of standardization**
Although standard record formats like FHIR and HL7 are becoming more common and new regulations are pushing Electronic Health Record (EHR) vendors to provide APIs that

support interoperability, many providers and healthcare systems use customized EHR systems that can be hard to convert to a standard format and shared with others.

- **Limited budgets**

Not all organizations have the financial or technical resources they need to invest in the technical resources required to build a truly interoperable system. There may be some government grants available to update health records systems, so organizations should check to see if they are eligible. Many cloud vendors also offer pay-as-you-go payment models that could make technical expenses more affordable and predictable.

- **Diverse technology needs**

Organizations need to follow different rules and regulations depending on what type of care they provide and where they are located, so many organizations have highly customized data. Organizations can help connect different internal and external systems through a hybrid cloud platform that gives them options to combine and integrate their data without sacrificing the customizations they need.

- **Legacy systems**

Healthcare organizations with older legacy systems face the dual challenges of modernizing their systems while also meeting interoperability requirements. Organizations can meet both goals using a hybrid cloud approach to extract data from legacy systems and make it more accessible for modern applications and programs. This approach gives organizations the option to keep data moving while they work on updating their systems.

- **Security**

Healthcare organizations can find it hard to balance the need for health information to be accessible with the need to secure sensitive information and maintain patient privacy, especially with the increasing number of cybersecurity attacks on healthcare systems.

- **Consent**

The consent management for health-related data may be required in certain circumstances, where the other legal bases under article 9 of the EU Reg. 2016/679 (GDPR) could not find application.

- **Professional burdens**

When new tools for recordkeeping are introduced, people need to learn how to use them. Healthcare professionals are often wary about new systems since EHR systems often do a better job supporting administrative and billing workflows than clinicians' needs.

- **Heterogeneous landscape of healthcare systems in Europe**

Healthcare in Europe is for historical reasons and by definition of the European Treaties a pluralistic field: each country, and even regions, have their own healthcare system. Different national or regional health systems use different laws, policies, and terminologies. This further increases the complexity of communicating effectively and efficiently.

3.3. European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

Within the European landscape, COM(2017)134 from the European Commission adopted on 23 March 2017, establishes the basis for the development of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) and gives specific guidance on how to set up interoperable digital public services. It offers public administrations 47 concrete recommendations on how to improve governance of their interoperability activities, establish cross-organisational relationships, streamline processes supporting end-to-end digital services, and ensure that both existing and new legislation do not compromise interoperability efforts. The new EIF is undertaken in the

context of the Commission priority to create a Digital Single Market in Europe and valuable guidelines for the development of VALKYRIES can be drawn from its contents.

What are the main motivations for this text? Mainly, provide guidance, improve quality of Public Services and foster digital collaboration for Public Administrations and European Institutions by following a common approach. Within the EIF we can find several principles that must drive interoperability actions, among them are data portability; openness; user centricity; inclusion and accessibility; and reusability. In addition, the Conceptual Model seen in the EIF (*Figure 1*) represents the levels on which effort is focused are technical, organisational, semantic and legal interoperability. The intention is to promote the sharing and reuse of common infrastructures, services and IT systems; to simplify the organisation, streamline the processes and listen to the needs of business and citizens; to structure the data in commonly agreed formats; and to propose clear and coherent legislation and policies.

Figure 1 - EIF Conceptual Model

Some of the supporting interoperability solutions that are embodied in the EIF are the European Interoperability Reference Architecture, which enables development, assessment, sharing and reuse of interoperable solutions supporting public services; a cartography tool, which provides access/maintenance to/of a cartography of solutions supporting portfolio decisions and sharing, discovery and reuse of solutions; the JOINUP IoP solutions catalogue, that helps Public Administrations in offering modern, user friendly and interoperable public services; the Interoperability Maturity Model, which consists of an online self-assessment that provides a fast & tangible view of public services' interoperability as well as targeted advice on how to improve interoperability performance; the NIFO outcomes; and the sharing and reuse framework, which helps Public Administrations in reusing, sharing or jointly developing IT solutions.

As stipulated in the Treaties of the European Union (EU), the EU's internal market guarantees four 'freedoms', the free movement of goods, capital, services and people between the 28 Member States. These freedoms are assured by common policies supported by interconnected, interoperable networks and systems. In doing so, they inevitably have to interact electronically with Member State public administrations. To make these interactions efficient, effective, timely and of high quality, and to help reduce the cost and effort involved, Member States are modernising their public administrations by introducing digital public services. However, they risk creating isolated digital environments and, consequently, electronic barriers that may prevent public administrations from connecting with each other, and citizens and businesses from identifying and using available digital public services in countries other than their own. For this reason, efforts to digitise the public sector should be well coordinated at European and national levels to avoid digital fragmentation of services and data, and help the EU's digital single market to work smoothly.

At the same time, the challenges facing the Union require common policy responses from the Member States and the Commission, through EU legislation that requires interaction across borders and policy sectors. This also involves setting up and running interoperable systems. Such systems, as set out in the digital single market strategy, are intended to ensure effective communication between digital components such as devices, networks and data repositories. They also provide more efficient connections across borders, between communities and between public services and authorities.

The EIF is principally promoted and maintained by the ISA² programme in close cooperation between the Member States and the Commission in the spirit of Articles 26, 170 and 171 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union calling for the establishment of interoperable trans-European networks that will enable citizens to derive full benefit from a European internal market. *Figure 2* shows the interoperability storyline represented in the EIF, from its first version to the latest one, and looking at the various programmes, directives and regulations in this respect.

Figure 2 - EIF interoperability storyline

3.4. VALKYRIES approach to interoperability

As mentioned, VALKYRIES aims at analyzing, improving and demonstrating infrastructures, protocols and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during the deployment, intervention and local and remote coordination of first responders. To achieve this, several important lines of effort will be pursued and one of them, the improvement of interoperability, is the subject of this document. The study will take into account the essential levels of legal,

organisational, semantic and technical interoperability proposed by the EIF but will also pay special attention to ethical synergy. In the following, the different sections of interest will be presented, supported by an in-depth bibliographical but also pragmatic analysis, where challenges but also opportunities will appear.

4. Ethical-legal profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities

4.1. Ethical interoperability

As it is well known, for all activities funded by the European Union, fundamental rights protection and EU values enhancement are an integral part of technical research and innovation from beginning to end. Therefore, ethical-legal compliance is seen as pivotal to achieve real research excellence. There is a clear need to make an assessment of the activities from the conceptual stage of the proposal not only to respect the legal framework but also to enhance the quality of the research. An ethical-legal approach adopted by design boosts the opportunity to generate an ethical-legal compliant result by default. VALKYRIES is fully aware of the need to develop its research and proposal tasks under the umbrella of ethical-legal compliance, ensuring that the processes are correct and the solution offered is viable.

Going into more detail, with a view to exploring the challenges and opportunities of ethical interoperability, it is worth noting that this area is one of the most widely understood and cooperative. The commitment to the European Charter of Fundamental Rights, the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols, the European Charter for Researchers, national legislations, and Regulation (EU) 2016/679, is appreciated and there is a commitment to defend them. But the pace must not slow down, on the contrary, we must continue to strive to consolidate it even further. In this respect, and with a particular focus on the sector of first responders in emergency situations, VALKYRIES is looking for effective bottom-up approaches to share a cultural change towards research and innovation. The emergency situations we work on involve the participation of all kinds of actors, different information packages and even cross-border exchanges. All of this is done with the intention of improving the response, both in terms of quality and agility, but with the awareness that in the process there is a great deal of sensitive data that must be protected.

The advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the past decades has led to the wide adoption of electronic healthcare and emergency response systems. This has in actual fact led to the improvement in the quality of healthcare and first response by enhancing the collection, storage, retrieval and access to health information. But it has also brought with it an enormous commitment to ensure data privacy, confidentiality, control of access to victims' information, the commercialization of de-identified victims' information and ownership of patients' information, which are associated with the interoperability of electronic healthcare systems. It is clear that in certain emergency situations actors from different institutions and even from different countries will have to collaborate, sharing relevant information in order to confront the situation and overcome the emergency, but this must be done with respect for human rights and ensuring that the process is limited to what is strictly necessary. The challenges must be met as objectively and professionally as possible, without any discrimination or irregularities. In the course of the VALKYRIES project, sustainability standards for the sharing of sensitive data as health data in the context of medical research will be defined, with specific regards to the protection of involved subjects' fundamental rights. These sustainability standards will be defined on the basis of a balancing test, which identifies the regulatory level that maximises innovation, research and data subjects' protection for each of the applicable access regimes. Our paramount goal is to promote Open Science in a robust, privacy-preserving, and efficient environment.

As Olaronke and Olaleke (2015) comment, in the context of health care and first responders, interoperability can be viewed as the ability of systems to exchange information in a seamless way, use the information that has been exchanged meaningfully and also possess the ability to work together within and across organizational boundaries with the aim of providing improved

services for individuals, communities, nations and the world at large. The use of information meaningfully in the definition above refers to the ability of electronic healthcare systems to improve the quality, safety, efficiency, and reduce health disparities; engage patients and family in care process, improve care coordination, population and public health, as well as maintain privacy and security of patient health information. Thus, the concept of interoperability in healthcare can simply be described as the ability of System X to represent health information unambiguously as well as transmit the information (such as medications, drug names, diagnoses, allergies, immunizations, vital signs and chronic conditions) to System Y. Furthermore, System Y must be able to understand the meaning of the transmitted information, and use it for the purpose that was intended for by System X. In any such situation that arises, there shall be an obligation to implement appropriate measures to ensure the integrity, authenticity, confidentiality, availability, traceability, quality, protection, retrieval and physical and logical preservation of all electronic documents, their carriers and media.

On the other hand, apart from the legal obligation to protect the information of those concerned, it can be established that the ethical interoperability dilemma is not due to a failure to comply with established principles and rights, but that certain technological and organisational constraints are preventing the response from being as good as it could be. In other words, it is the lack of interoperability that is unethical. The fact that the different institutions do not share common semantics, that the means of communication of each actor are different, that the organisational processes do not follow the same steps, among other things, are making the service unsatisfactory and the response highly improbable. There are a variety of complex and redundant elements whose inefficiency compromises patient safety, quality of care, generates clinical fatigue and wastes huge amounts of money that could be spent elsewhere. The ethical commitment is to improve all these tools and processes and to ensure that money is not wasted on circumventing obstacles.

4.1.1. Comparative analysis of existing studies on ethical issues in electronic healthcare systems

Several studies have been conducted on ethical issues in electronic healthcare systems. According to Beauchamp and Childress (2011), the four basic ethical principles that are pertinent to electronic healthcare systems include autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice. Snyder and Gauthier (2008) viewed the principles of dignity and veracity as basic ethical principles in electronic healthcare systems in addition to the four basic ethical principles developed by Beauchamp and Childress. Accordingly, the principle of dignity is based on the idea that all persons have the right to be treated with respect and dignity. Dignity includes respect for their emotions, relationships, reasonable goals, privacy, and bodily integrity. Veracity is the right of individuals to be provided with complete, accurate and truthful information about their medical conditions at the point of diagnosis or treatment. On the other hand, Reidl (2005) emphasized that the basic ethical principles of electronic healthcare systems include the principles of transparency, standardization, work ethics, privacy and confidentiality as well as the principle of equitable allocation of healthcare resources. The principle of transparency is the process of providing the users of the electronic healthcare system with a valid and simple model of the system. This implies that the users must have adequate knowledge of the effects of the system on their activities. The standardization principle ensures that the standards used by electronic healthcare systems do not interfere with the local work practices of healthcare practitioners, whereas the work ethics principle ensures that the ICT facilities used in the healthcare system augment the activities of healthcare practitioners. The principle of privacy and confidentiality ensures that the electronic healthcare system provides surveillance to its users. This ensures that unauthorized access to electronic health information is prevented. The principle of equitable allocation of healthcare resources ensures that healthcare facilities are available to all individuals at the point of care.

In addition, the ethical principles of electronic healthcare systems according to the International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) code of conduct include the principles of information-privacy and disposition, openness, security, access, legitimate infringement and the principle of accountability. The principle of information-privacy and disposition emphasizes that all individuals must have a fundamental right to control the collection, storage, access, use, communication, manipulation and disposition of data about themselves. The principle of openness ensures that the collection, storage, access, use, communication, manipulation and disposition of personal data are released in an appropriate and timely fashion to the subject of those data. The principle of security guarantees that health information is protected against loss, degradation, unauthorized access and destruction. The principle of access ensures that an individual has the right to access his information and the right to modify his information with respect to accuracy, completeness and relevance. The principle of legitimate infringement ensures that the fundamental right of control over the collection, storage, access, use, manipulation, communication and disposition of personal data is conditioned only by the legitimate, appropriate and relevant data needs of a free, responsible and democratic society; while the principle of accountability ensures that any infringement of the privacy right of an individual is justified in an appropriate and in a timely manner (Olaronke and Olaleke, 2015).

Some of the challenges mentioned above can be faced if the following recommendations are followed:

- Anonymisation and pseudonymisation of victim's information.
- Informed consent of victims.
- Adequate security measures (i.e., monitoring; audit trail, etc.).

4.2. Organisational interoperability

In order to get rid of the obstacles above mentioned, it is essential to understand the concept of organisational interoperability. This will help us not only to address the ethical challenges, but also the legal and technical challenges discussed below, as the need to improve organisational synergies will appear in all of them. According to the EIF, organisational interoperability refers to the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. In practice, organisational interoperability means documenting and integrating or aligning business processes and relevant information exchanged. It also aims to meet the requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused.

Cooperation between public administrations is essential to provide services to citizens and to guarantee their rights. Such cooperation requires conditions that allow it to run smoothly, which requires interoperability. This facilitates the realisation of citizens' principles and rights; cooperation in the development and delivery of public services; and greater effectiveness and efficiency in the deployment and delivery of services. Additionally, continuity of care is a key priority for modern healthcare delivery. In turn, relies on seamless communication between all actors involved in the healthcare process. In fact, it is shown that the failure to ensure "common information" sharing is a cause of failure in the response phase (Desmond, 1998). Organizational considerations must align with external organizations and work towards achieving trust across stakeholders to enable meaningful data sharing.

There are multiple challenges to achieving high organisational interoperability. These include limited and fragmented budget cycles and funding, limited and fragmented planning and coordination and, in general, a high level of heterogeneity. Within the latter, we can find technological heterogeneity (i.e., organizations use different computer-based tools), data heterogeneity (i.e., each organization may assume a given information model) and informatisation heterogeneity (i.e., some organization may adopt a Geographic Information

System (GIS) (Cai, 2005) or collaborative tools (Erl, 2005), while others only deal with paper-based documents or rather simple computer-based tools). Some of the obstacles mentioned above are difficult to remove in the short term as there are many issues to be addressed and each organisation has a different economic and procedural pace. In any case, the implementation of measures should follow the following key principles:

- Measures shall not interfere with Member States' competences and shall not harmonise any laws or regulations of the Member States and shall fully respect the responsibilities of the Member States for the organisation and delivery of health services and medical care.
- Existing ICT infrastructure in each Member State shall be respected. Measures towards interoperability shall evolve from existing ICT infrastructures.
- Users and in particular healthcare providers shall be involved at every stage in the refinement and implementation of these policy actions.

Nevertheless, Member States are expected to complement EU-level actions (identified in the interoperability action plan) with national actions, thus ensuring coherence, essential for the successful application of interoperability in the public sector in the Union. The interoperability action plan addresses issues related to the identification of solid mechanisms to govern interoperability at national level and across borders, collaboration between organisations, engagement of stakeholders, and awareness-raising on the benefits of interoperability. It also covers the development, improvement and promotion of key interoperability enablers and supporting instruments, while considering the needs and priorities of end users.

At the organisational level, procedures must be "understandable" by all parties by sharing common approaches. The standards in eHealth are reaching maturity at the international level with HL7 in eHealth and DICOM in imaging. But other standards are also important such as standards defined by World Wide Consortium (W3C) for web services recommendations, IEEE (ISO IEEE 11073-X) for devices and OASIS for security standards (SAML, XACML, ...) and other communication protocols.

There are three important actions that agencies must take to ensure interoperable communications are available for first responders in critical moments:

1. To plan in advance.
2. To establish and maintain relationships.
3. To adopt and integrate new technology into a communications plan when appropriate.

4.2.1. Business process alignment

Different administrative entities may need to align their existing business processes or define and establish new ones in order to work together efficiently and effectively to provide European public services. Aligning business processes implies documenting them in an agreed way and with commonly accepted modelling techniques, including the associated information exchanged so that all public administrations contributing to the delivery of European public services can understand the overall (end-to-end) business process and their role in it. This is in line with Recommendation 28 of the EIF.

4.2.2. Organisational relationships

The service orientation that underpins the conceptual model for public services necessitates a clear definition of the relationship between service providers and service consumers. This involves finding instruments to formalise mutual assistance, joint action and interconnected business processes as part of service provision e.g., MoUs and SLAs between participating public

administrations. For cross-border actions, these should preferably be multilateral or global European agreements. This is in line with Recommendation 29 of the EIF.

4.2.3. Governance interoperability

The EIF states that interoperability governance refers to decisions on interoperability frameworks, institutional arrangements, organisational structures, roles and responsibilities, policies, agreements and other aspects of ensuring and monitoring interoperability at national and EU levels. The EIF, the Interoperability Action Plan and the European Interoperability Architecture (EIRA) are important parts of interoperability governance at the EU level. European public services operate in a complex and changing environment. Political support is necessary for cross-sectoral and/or cross-border interoperability efforts to facilitate cooperation between public administrations. For effective cooperation, all stakeholders must share a vision, agree on objectives and timeframes and align priorities. Interoperability between public administrations at different administrative levels will only be successful if governments give sufficient priority and assign resources to their respective interoperability efforts.

Interoperability governance is the key to a holistic approach to interoperability, as it brings together all the instruments needed to apply it. Coordination, communication and monitoring are of the utmost importance for successful governance. The European Commission, through the ISA2 programme, supports a National Interoperability Framework Observatory (NIFO). Its main objective is to provide information about NIFs and related interoperability and digital strategies/policies, to help public administrations share and reuse experiences and to support the 'transposition' of the EIF nationally. A NIF can be one or more documents that define frameworks, policies, strategies, guidelines and action plans on interoperability in a Member State.

Governance interoperability should cover all layers: legal, organisational, semantic and technical. Ensuring interoperability when developing legal instruments, organizational business processes, information exchange, services, and components that support European public services is a continuous task, as changes in the environment frequently disrupt interoperability. It necessitates organizational structures and the assignment of roles and responsibilities for the delivery and operation of public services, service level agreements, the establishment and management of interoperability agreements, change management procedures, and business continuity and data quality plans, among other things.

Integrated public service governance should include as a minimum:

- The definition of organisational structures, allocation of roles and responsibilities and the decision-making process for the stakeholders involved.
- The imposition of requirements for:
 - aspects of interoperability including legal pre-conditions, quality, scalability and availability of reusable building blocks including information sources (base registries, open data portals, etc.) and other interconnected services.
 - external information/services, translated into clear service level agreements (including on interoperability).
- An adaptation management plan, to define the procedures and processes needed to deal with and control changes.
- A business continuity/disaster recovery plan to ensure that digital public services and their building blocks continue to work in a range of situations, e.g., cyberattacks or the failure of building blocks.

4.2.4. Global Consortium for eHealth Interoperability

Internationally, efforts to improve organisational interoperability are being seen in the creation of the Global Consortium for eHealth Interoperability. This organism enables national governmental agencies, health systems and their stakeholders to leverage emerging interoperability standards and the latest implementation guidance to achieve better, lower-cost health outcomes by decreasing barriers and accelerating the rapid, coordinated, efficient deployment of next-generation, API-based interoperable standards.

Unique in the healthcare industry, the Consortium convenes stakeholders around the world to share validated, scalable interoperability best practices at the point of care to:

- Support the implementation of safe, usable and effective health data standards.
- Accelerate the development and adoption of secure and open standards-based APIs.
- Define an on-ramp for exchange via APIs.
- Facilitate the establishment of implementation communities around the world.

The Consortium supports National government agencies; health systems and their associated clinicians; non-governmental organizations such as standards development organizations; industry and patient-focused, caused-based associations; and market suppliers such as IT software/hardware and medical device developers. All this is done with the aim of delivering high-quality and efficient healthcare. Despite progress toward better health outcomes, a lack of interoperable data formats, incomplete information exchange across the continuum of care, and business governance that inhibits data interoperability, all limit the ability to have a broader impact on better outcomes, stifling increased innovation in the healthcare marketplace.

HIMSS, HL7 International and IHE International together believe an entity like the Global Consortium for eHealth Interoperability can activate digital health efficiency and innovation on the ground by deploying validated, scalable, data-sharing technologies and processes to support best practices at the point of care and beyond. The consortium will act as a coordinating point for the global healthcare community to help accelerate the adoption of next-generation, API-based standards to support increased interoperability around the world. The motivation lies in creating a trusted environment, sharing actionable knowledge, drive continuous improvement and accelerate progress.

5. Legal profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities

DECISION 922/2009/EC defends that continuous efforts are needed in order to ensure cross-border and cross-sectoral interoperability, to exchange experience, establish and maintain common and shared approaches, specifications, standards and solutions and to assess the ICT implications of Community legislation with a view to supporting efficient and effective cross-border interactions, inter alia, in the implementation of that legislation, while reducing administrative burdens and costs. Helping to meet these needs is one of VALKYRIES' objectives and that is why this document will incorporate the advances and improvements developed in the different tasks and Use Cases.

In addition, the VALKYRIES project, in its description of the action, established that from a regulatory and standardization perspective, the compliance activity relies on the analysis of the complex legal-ethical framework from a comparative perspective to identify possible practical gaps to be harmonized and re-interpreted in terms of contractual conditions between different stakeholders. For these purposes, specific attention is given to the legal framework of access regimes regarding data concerning health. Regulatory responses, such as the one given by the recently enacted Open Data Directive (Dir. EU 2019/1024), place particular emphasis on the value of access and transferability of research data, in consistency with the paradigm of open science and innovation, aiming at fostering the interaction between research results and market innovation. Ethical legal compliance, indeed, is a pre-condition for data sharing.

In the European integration society we live in, it is undeniable that following harmonized procedures is an essential part of the enforcement process to provide protection of citizens, especially in cross-border scenarios. There are a large number of common projects, in the field of health and emergency management but also in many others, that require improved interoperability. There are several fronts on which progress can be made, but legal interoperability is essential to ensure that everything is well supported. This is of paramount importance to ensure that solutions follow established processes, meet EU objectives and uphold enacted principles and rights. However, in order to be effectively implemented, interoperability of other issues, such as semantic and syntactic interoperability, must also be addressed.

5.1. Legal interoperability

The concept of legal interoperability covers the broader environment of laws, policies, procedures and cooperation agreements needed to allow the seamless exchange of information between different organisations, regions and countries (Wardle, 2018). It is about ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are able to work together. This might require that legislation does not block the establishment of European public services within and between Member States and that there are clear agreements about how to deal with differences in legislation across borders, including the option of putting in place new legislation. Furthermore, it also relates to license interoperability, that is the possibility of legally mixing data coming from different sources and using them within a broad range of projects and business models. Legal interoperability is a particularly relevant topic in the context of medical research and emergency cooperation, where datasets are most of the times encumbered with an array of different intellectual property rights. In this perspective, legal interoperability ultimately relates to the coordination of different right-holders. Additionally, it also concerns situations where regulatory or policy measures may enable or restrict the flows of personal and non-personal data.

In particular, if we consider the current EU data strategy, scientific progress and innovation are driven by the principle that data flows shall be managed as close as necessary and as open as possible. Therefore, limits to data sharing could be justified only if based on prevalent interests. Examples include legal restrictions based on intellectual property law, national security, commercial interests, the protection of endangered species or privacy regulations, such as the GDPR. Several mechanisms are used in practice to restrict access to data where such regulatory or policy measures exist, e.g., data redaction, data generalisation, data anonymisation, or simply restricting any access to the data.

It is worth noting that there are a number of “enabling legal instruments” that support legal interoperability and the implementation of FAIR or Open Data Principles. Such enabling legal instruments may come in the form of EU directives and regulations, national laws, EU and national policies, international agreements, contractual agreements, individual or institutional policies and other forms of practice that may incorporate broader policy considerations. An example of such an enabling legal instrument is the Open Data Directive, which requires that research data generated by public sector bodies (and funded by the public) follows the principle of ‘open by default’ and is made available in a manner compatible with the FAIR Principles, which we will explain in the following sections. However, there is a need to examine whether obligations or recommendations to use certain licences, in particular at the national level, are coherent with specific recommendations that are or may be adopted by the Interoperability Framework.

Legal interoperability covers the broader environment of laws, policies, procedures and cooperation agreements needed to allow the seamless exchange of information and reusability of data between different individuals, organisations and across jurisdictions. It occurs among multiple datasets from different sources when:

- The legal use conditions are clearly and readily determinable for each of the datasets, typically through automated means.
- The legal use conditions imposed on each dataset allow the creation and use of combined or derivative products.
- Users may legally access and use each dataset without seeking authorisation from data generators on a case-by-case basis assuming that the accumulated conditions of use for each and all of the datasets are met.

From COM(2017)134 we can understand that the first step towards addressing legal interoperability is to identify pre-conditions to make data flows interoperable. In particular, to perform ‘interoperability checks’ by screening existing legislation to identify interoperability barriers: sectoral or geographical restrictions in the use and storage of data, different and vague data licence models, over-restrictive obligations to use specific digital technologies or delivery modes to provide public services, contradictory requirements for the same or similar business processes, outdated security and data protection needs, etc. Also, coherence between legislation, in view of ensuring interoperability, should be assessed before adoption and through evaluating their performance regularly once they are put into application.

Keeping in mind that European public services are clearly intended to be delivered via digital channels, ICT must be considered as early as possible in the law-making process. In particular, proposed legislation should undergo a ‘digital check’ to ensure that it suits not only the physical but also the digital world (e.g., the internet); to identify any barriers to digital exchange; and to identify and assess its ICT impact on stakeholders. This will facilitate interoperability between public services at lower levels (semantic and technical) as well, and increase the potential for reusing existing ICT solutions, reducing cost and implementation time. What is clear, however, is that in any case the legal value of any information exchanged between Member States should

be maintained across borders, and data protection national safeguards in both originating and receiving countries complied with. This might require cross-impact assessments to identify technical and organizational measures to overcome potential differences in the implementation of the applicable legislation, namely the GDPR.

5.1.1. Key legal issues

Within the legal framework, which is already complicated as each country has its own particularities, some issues need to be understood. First of all, the relationship between law and interoperability must be understood as a multidirectional network. Legal interoperability should make systems work together, but not make the systems all the same, since regulatory competition can be advantageous and productive provided the best normative order prevails (Palfrey and Gasser, 2012).

Higher levels of legal interoperability typically necessitate more careful design of governmental regulations as well as rule disclosure in order to increase legal certainty. The highest level would be achieved if all normative rules were harmonized. However, total harmonization should not be the approach to take in all cases because, on the one hand, such a framework cannot account for the cultural diversity of societies in the global online world and, on the other hand, would be a utopian wish in reality. Moreover, it is important to find the appropriate degree of legal interoperability (instead of an all-or-nothing solution) considering the substantive principles (such as freedom of expression or privacy) in different circumstances. (Weber, 2014).

As a result, legal operability is a matter of degrees: a very high level of legal interoperability may cause difficulties in applying harmonized rules at the national level (for example, due to the difficulty of reaching harmonized interpretation methods), whereas a very low level of legal interoperability may cause challenges in smooth (social or economic) interaction. As with the appropriate level of interconnectedness, rule makers must determine the optimal level of legal interoperability.

As Weber comments, a method to potentially address the issue of “adequate” or “optimum” levels of legal interoperability could be to apply different regulatory models and mechanisms (according to the given circumstances) that can enable, based on past experience, certain levels of legal interoperability within certain contexts. Consequently, the assessment of the degree and scope of legal interoperability, as well as its method of approach, depends on the substantive topic at hand.

Some key legal issues that will be explored throughout VALKYRIES are the following:

- The formula “as close as necessary” can be addressed following the principles framing the applicable legislations.
- Data protection: according to the principles of minimization, purposes, and necessity personal data could be processed only if proper technical and organizational measures identified by the data controller mitigate the risks for the availability confidentiality and integrity of data flows. In this regard, pseudonymization is a technical and at the same time organizational safeguard that could satisfy the necessity to preserve individual confidentiality enabling a data sharing ecosystem.
- Intellectual property rights protection could be considered a limit to openness as licenses and patentability needs could temporary / territorially / sectorial identify conditions to not sharing information.
- The risk of misuse of shared information could define further limits to openness.

5.1.2. Governance interoperability

Previously, we have discussed NIFOs definition of governance interoperability, which refers to decisions on interoperability frameworks, institutional arrangements, organisational structures, roles and responsibilities, policies, agreements and other aspects of ensuring and monitoring interoperability at national and EU levels. In this regard, and in relation to legal interoperability, it would be helpful if national legislative bodies could agree on the development of laws related to cross-border collaboration and exchange. Encouraging these bodies to communicate so that they can develop bodies of law in sync would be a huge boost to achieving better legal interoperability. Each country is free and sovereign over its laws but, at the level of the EU, which is an international integration organisation with the ambition of facilitating the movement of goods and people within its territory, it would be wise to foresee that emergency situations will arise in which several countries will be involved.

In the Lisbon Ministerial Declaration of 19 September 2007, Ministers invited the Commission, inter alia, to facilitate cooperation among Member States and the Commission to define, develop, implement and monitor cross-border and cross-sectoral interoperability, and stated that future Community legislation should, in particular, anticipate and assess the impact of that legislation on ICT infrastructures and service transformation. In order to meet these challenges, such efforts should be made through close cooperation, coordination and dialogue between the Commission and the Member States, in close interaction with the sectors responsible for the implementation of European Union policies and, where appropriate, with other stakeholders, giving due consideration to the priorities and the linguistic diversity of the European Union and to the development of common approaches on key issues.

5.1.3. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles

The guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 state that data-intensive science and innovation and the exponential growth in the quantity of research data requires that humans and machines can make better use of knowledge discovery, and access to integration and analysis of research data (including publications, digital objects, metadata and software). The recent COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of this, as well as the ethical and legal dimensions of open and fair data sharing. , i.e., making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. It is emphasised, among other things, that research data should be open by default while considering the need to balance openness and the protection of scientific information, commercialisation and intellectual property rights, privacy concerns and security, following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

The body of laws at EU level which directly affects legal interoperability is fairly limited and includes intellectual property (in particular copyright, database rights), data protection and laws aimed at protecting sensitive or confidential data. There are however additional legal instruments and strategies that may also affect, directly or indirectly, legal interoperability. In parallel, as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) comments, there are certain ‘enabling’ legal instruments, soft law and policies that support and promote the application of either Open Data or FAIR Data Principles, or both, at least to the extent that the data is produced or funded by the public sector.

In order to make progress in understanding, it is necessary to carry out a legal dogmatics analysis, providing in-depth knowledge and an overview of current legal norms relevant to legal interoperability and clarifying the legal framework that is relevant and may be applicable to emergency response situations, including search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in which several regions or countries are affected and hence greater interoperability being required. The purpose of the legal dogmatic analysis is to describe, analyse, clarify, interpret, evaluate and

systemise the content of valid current norms. The legal dogmatic method combines a literature review with the mapping of relevant legal sources (regulation, directives, national laws, case law, soft law, etc.).

The FAIR Data Principles, first coined in 2014 and published in 2016, are a set of guiding principles that seek to increase the reusability of data and digital objects (including data-related algorithms, tools, workflows, protocols, services and other kinds of digital and research objects). They put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals. The success of implementing the FAIR data principles, i.e., the ability of the research community to share, access, and reuse data, as well as to integrate data from diverse sources, requires, among other aspects, the free flow of research data without unnecessary constraints, allowing for discovery and interoperability within EOSC.

Some recommendations made by the EOSC are the following:

- Open access to research data is an enabler of legal interoperability. The promotion of FAIR principles should go hand-in-hand with efforts to make data open in accordance with the principle that data must be “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”.
- Copyrightable metadata should be free from any restrictions and assigned a public domain waiver. The Creative Commons No Rights Reserved (CC0) or the Public Domain Dedication and Licence (PDDL), or an equivalent statement of rights should be preferred.
- Metadata should include a standardised human and machine-readable statement of rights, legal restrictions, applicable licences, and, where relevant, additional conditions of use (including applicable jurisdictions) of the data that they are assigned to.
- The EOSC should provide a mechanism, for example in the Rules of Participation, or by way of guidance, to facilitate the implementation of the recommendation above in a harmonised manner.
- All copyrightable components of the research data and their respective licences should be clearly identified in the metadata and assigned the correct rights-holder. In the case of database (*sui generis*) rights in repositories, the applicable (permissive) licence should be included in the terms of use of the repository.
- Copyrightable data should be FAIR and, to the greatest extent possible, be made part of the public domain or assigned a permissive licence, unless legal or legitimate reasons apply.

6. Technical profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities

6.1. Technical interoperability

HIMSS states that the health interoperability ecosystem comprises individuals, systems and processes that want to share, exchange and access all forms of health information, including discrete, narrative and multimedia. Individuals, patients, providers, hospitals/health systems, researchers, payers, suppliers and systems are potential stakeholders within this ecosystem. Each is involved in the creation, exchange and use of health information and/or data. An efficient interoperability ecosystem provides an information infrastructure that uses technical standards, policies and protocols to enable seamless and secure capture, discovery, exchange and utilization of health information as well as other data related to the operation in question.

As DIRECTIVE 2011/24/EU comments, it is a reality that technological developments in cross-border provision of healthcare through the use of ICTs may result in the exercise of supervisory responsibilities by Member States being unclear, and can thus hinder the free movement of emergency response and healthcare and give rise to possible additional risks to health protection and incident management. Widely different and incompatible formats and standards are used for provision of healthcare using ICTs throughout the European Union, creating both obstacles to this mode of cross-border healthcare provision and possible risks to health protection. Therefore, it is necessary for Member States to aim at interoperability of ICT systems.

According to the definition provided by COCIR, the European Trade Association representing the medical imaging, radiotherapy, health ICT and electromedical industries, technical interoperability refers to the ability of two or more information and communication technology applications, to accept data from each other and perform a given task in an appropriate and satisfactory manner without the need for extra operator intervention. To achieve interoperability in emergency situations for a given use case, all aspects of interoperability have to be concerned and should be based on common technical and semantic standards. The EIF objective is to inspire European public administrations in their efforts to design and deliver seamless European public services to other public administrations, citizens and businesses which are to the degree possible, digital-by-default (i.e., providing services and data preferably via digital channels), cross-border by-default (i.e. accessible for all citizens in the EU) and open-by-default (i.e. enabling reuse, participation/access and transparency).

The NIFO comments that aspects of technical interoperability include interface specifications, interconnection services, data integration services, data presentation and exchange, and secure communication protocols. A major obstacle to interoperability arises from legacy systems. Historically, applications and information systems in public administrations were developed in a bottom-up fashion, trying to solve domain-specific and local problems. This resulted in fragmented ICT islands which are difficult to interoperate. Due to the size of public administration and the fragmentation of ICT solutions, the plethora of legacy systems creates an additional interoperability barrier in the technical layer. Therefore, technical interoperability should be ensured, whenever possible, via the use of formal technical specifications.

In general, as discussed, interoperability refers to the ability of emergency responders to work seamlessly with other systems or products without any special effort. Wireless communications interoperability specifically refers to the ability of emergency response officials to share information via voice and data signals on demand, in real-time, when needed, and as authorized (Yarali, 2020). For example, when communications systems are interoperable, police and firefighters responding to a routine incident can talk to each other to coordinate efforts.

Communications interoperability also makes it possible for emergency response agencies responding to catastrophic accidents or disasters to work effectively together. Finally,, it allows emergency response personnel to maximize resources in planning for major predictable events, or for disaster relief and recovery efforts. Emergency managers must ensure that their communications capabilities are fully compatible with the capabilities of local law enforcement, fire and medical first responders, as well as with national agencies.

Some key issues that adversely affect emergency response wireless communications have been identified:

- Incompatible and aging communications equipment.
- Limited and fragmented radio spectrum.
- Limited equipment standards.

6.1.1. Standardization

In order to address the technical obstacles, as well as legal, ethical, organisational or any other, that first responders and other actors are encountering in emergency situations, it is highly recommended to strive for standardisation. Standards provide a common language and a common set of expectations that enable interoperability between systems and/or devices. For the purpose of seamlessly digest information about an individual and improve the overall coordination and delivery of emergency response, standards permit authorities, emergency services, clinicians, labs, hospitals, and patients to share data regardless of application or market supplier (HIMSS).

Identifying and selecting standards and specifications are fundamental to interoperability. According to the EIF, there are six steps to managing them appropriately:

- Identifying candidate standards and specifications based upon specific needs and requirements.
- Assessing candidate standards and specifications using standardised, transparent, fair and non-discriminatory methods.
- Implementing the standards and specifications according to plans and practical guidelines.
- Monitoring compliance with the standards and specifications;
- Managing change with appropriate procedures.
- Documenting standards and specifications, in open catalogues, using a standardised description.

In the field of health IT, there are approximately 40 different Standard Developing Organizations (SDOs). Health Level Seven (HL7), Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED) International, and the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium are some of the organizations that create standards (CDISC). Others, such as Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE), do not create new standards; instead, they combine complementing base standards into IHE profiles, which are then balloted. This creates a scenario that helps drive adoption of the base standards by providing implementation guidance that describes how multiple standards can be used together to support interoperable health information exchange. The different SDOs and profiling organizations have varying compositions and processes, but generally follow shared principles based on developing standards through a multi-stakeholder, consensus-based process to respond to specific industry or market needs (HIMSS).

Without standards and well-defined specifications, the interoperability of C2 systems can be quite challenging, technologically complex, time consuming and therefore expensive. As Gencturk et al (2015) comment, although there are some commonly used standards and specifications in command and control, sensor, disaster management and surveillance domains, there is no single specification on how to use these standards together when disparate systems need to interoperate. How can (disparate) systems (and users) exchange data, how can they communicate, and which rules should they follow?

6.1.2. Types of standards

As HIMSS aptly describes, in order to understand the types of health data standards available for use, these are commonly organised into the following specific categories: vocabulary/terminology, content, transport, privacy and security, and identifiers.

Vocabulary/Terminology Standards

Vocabulary/terminology standards address the ability of a sender and receiver of information to represent concepts in an unambiguous manner, which is a fundamental requirement for effective communication. Health information systems that communicate with each other rely on structured vocabularies, terminologies, code sets and classification systems to represent health concepts. Some common vocabulary standards currently used in the marketplace include:

- Current Procedural Terminology (CPT).
- Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System.
- ICD-10 and ICD-11.
- Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC).
- Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine-Clinical Terms (SNOMED-CT).
- Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).
- The Unified Code for Units of Measure.

Content Standards

Content standards relate to the data content within exchanges of information. They define the structure and organization of the electronic message or document's content. This standard category also includes the definition of common sets of data for specific message types:

- Consolidated CDA (C-CDA).
- HL7's Version 2.x (V2).
- HL7 Version 3 Clinical Document Architecture (CDA): It defines a clinical document as having the following six characteristics: persistence, stewardship, potential for authentication, context, wholeness and human readability.

Transport Standards

Transport standards address the format of messages exchanged between computer systems, document architecture, clinical templates, user interface and patient data linkage. Standards centre on "push" and "pull" methods for exchanging health information:

- Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM).
- Direct Standard™: Defines a set of standards and protocols to allow participants to send authenticated, encrypted health information directly to known, trusted recipients

over the internet. Two primary specifications are the Applicability Statement for Secure Health Transport v1.2 and the XDR and XDM for Direct Messaging.

- Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR®).
- IHE.
- Continua Design Guidelines.

Privacy and Security Standards

Privacy standards aim to protect an individual's (or organization's) right to determine whether, what, when, by whom and for what purpose their personal health information is collected, accessed, used or disclosed. Security standards define a set of administrative, physical and technical actions to protect the confidentiality, availability and integrity of health information:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- SAML and XACML.

Identifier Standards

Entities use identifier standards to uniquely identify patients or providers.

- Enterprise Master Patient Index (EMPI)
- Medical Record Number (MRN)
- National Provider ID (NPI)
- Object ID (OID): A globally unique ISO identifier and a preferred scheme for unique identifiers in HL7.

Implementation guide

An implementation guide is a document that comes with a standard and explains how to apply it to a specific healthcare use case. It should explain how a standard should be used in a certain use case, how data should be structured consistently, and what terminology should be used. While a standard can be implemented in a variety of ways, utilizing an implementation guide to integrate a standard into a health IT system directs one approach to limit the standard for a specific context, removing ambiguity and ensuring uniformity. They provide customers with a tool that simplifies, minimizes the cost, and alleviates the worry associated with deploying interoperable systems.

- Testing and Conformance Efforts:
- Conformity Assessment.
- eHealth Exchange Testing Program.
- HL7 FHIR® Connectathons.
- IHE Connectathons.
- Global Consortium for eHealth Interoperability.

6.2. Semantic interoperability

The semantic level of interoperability, also known as semantic transport, entails sharing data between systems that have completely distinct data structures. It refers to the meaning of data elements as well as their relationship. It entails creating vocabularies and schemata to describe data exchanges and ensuring that all communicating parties understand data pieces in the same way. Improved semantic interoperability, as advocated by JOINUP, a solution created by the European Commission to provide a common venue that facilitates public administrations, businesses and citizens communication and collaboration on IT projects across Europe, ensures

that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties. With it, images could be transferred from one system to another, interpreted and incorporated into the new system regardless of the original format or source of the image. Yet determining what data to collect and transfer can be difficult since systems have different ways of presenting the same information.

In more detail, it is the ability of computer systems to exchange data with unambiguous, shared meaning. Semantic interoperability is required for machine-computable logic, inference, knowledge discovery, and data federation between information systems. Therefore, it is concerned not just with the packaging of data (syntax), but the simultaneous transmission of the meaning with the data (semantics). This is accomplished by adding data about the data (metadata), linking each data element to a controlled, shared vocabulary. The meaning of the data is transmitted along with the data in a self-descriptive "information package" that is independent of any information system. This shared vocabulary, along with its links to an ontology, serves as the foundation and capability for machine interpretation, inference, and logic.

Perceiving data and information as a valuable public asset is a good point to start when it comes to improving semantic interoperability. In this sense, an information management strategy should be drafted and coordinated at the highest possible level (corporate or enterprise) to avoid fragmentation and set priorities. For example, agreements on reference data, in the form of taxonomies, controlled vocabularies, thesauri, code lists and reusable data structures/models are key prerequisites for achieving semantic interoperability (NIFO). Furthermore, approaches like data-driven design, coupled with linked data technologies, are innovative ways of substantially improving semantic interoperability.

To enable meaningful information exchange among European public organizations, robust, coherent, and universally applicable information standards and specifications are required, in the same way, that technical standards have fostered technical interoperability (e.g., network connectivity) for decades. Given the different linguistic, cultural, legal, and administrative environments in the Member States, this interoperability layer poses significant challenges. In this sense, in order to support the EU's digital single market, it will be difficult to ensure seamless information exchange, free movement of data, and data portability among Member States unless standardisation efforts in the semantic interoperability layer mature.

Interoperability has been the topic of many research projects, initiatives and pilots. Notably, CALLIOPE delivered the "eHealth Interoperability Roadmap" in December 2010. Currently, "Semantic Interoperability for Health Network (SemanticHealthNet)" aims to develop a scalable and sustainable pan-European process for semantic interoperability. Smart Open Services for European Patients (epSOS) is a European eHealth Pilot in which semantic interoperability standards are being tested in a reference implementation.

6.3. Syntactic interoperability

Semantic interoperability requires syntactic interoperability. The first refers to the ability of a system to correctly interpret the message structure of exchanged information and, as a result, to read its content, even if they are unaware of its meaning. Basically, the way in which data is communicated between components. HL7 has been in use in healthcare for over thirty years and uses the pipe character (|) as a data delimiter. The current internet standard for document markup is Extensible Markup Language (XML), which uses the data delimiter ">" as a delimiter. The data delimiters have no meaning in the data and only serve to structure it. Therefore, the data is meaningless without a data dictionary to translate the contents of the delimiters. While many attempts have been made to create data dictionaries and information models to go along with these data packaging mechanisms, none have proven to be practical to implement.

Syntactic interoperability, as provided by XML or Structured Query Language (SQL) standards, entails using a common data format and protocol to structure any data so that the method of processing the information can be deduced from the structure. It also detects syntactic errors, allowing receiving systems to request that any message that appears garbled or incomplete be resent. No semantic communication is possible if the syntax is garbled or unable to represent the data. However, information represented in one syntax may in some cases be accurately translated into a different syntax. Where accurate translation of syntaxes is possible, systems using different syntaxes may also interoperate accurately. In some cases, the ability to accurately translate information among systems using different syntaxes may be limited to one direction, when the formalisms used have different levels of expressivity (i.e., the ability to express information).

Because of the frequent production of new terms or the attribution of new meanings to existing terms, a single ontology encompassing representations of every term used in every application is widely regarded unachievable. While it is impossible to anticipate every concept that a user might want to represent in a computer, there is the possibility of finding a finite set of "primitive" concept representations that can be combined to create any of the more specific concepts that users might require for any given set of applications or ontologies. Having a foundation ontology that contains all those primitive elements would provide a sound basis for general semantic interoperability, and allow users to define any new terms they need by using the basic inventory of ontology elements, and still have those newly defined terms properly interpreted by any other computer system that can interpret the basic foundation ontology. The number of such primitive concept representations is currently being investigated to see if it is finite or will continue to grow indefinitely. If it is finite, then after some early foundation ontology has been tested and utilized by a wide range of users, a stable foundation ontology adequate for supporting accurate and general semantic interoperability can emerge. However, no foundation ontology has been adopted by a wide community to date.

6.4. Foundational interoperability

Interoperability at the foundational level is establishing the basic ability for two or more systems to exchange data. According to HIMMS, this level "allows data exchange from one information technology system to be received by another and does not require the ability for the receiving information technology system to interpret the data." An example of foundational interoperability would be sending laboratory results from one facility to another. The information would be correct and delivered securely, but would require manual data entry and interpretation. This level of interoperability, also known as simple transport, is the most basic. Data is securely transferred from one system or device to another without interpreting the data or transforming it into a particular format. For example, a nurse downloads a PDF file of a patient's latest lab results from the results portal of the lab, then manually enters the data into the patient's health record.

6.5. Structural interoperability

Structural interoperability defines the format of the data exchange that takes place between systems. This level basically focuses on the packaging of the data via message format standards. Specifically, structural interoperability defines the syntax of the data exchange, according to HIMSS. Messaging standards such as HL7, for example, provide guidance on how messages should be structured. HIMSS notes that this form of interoperability permits the "uniform movement" of health data from system to system where the "clinical or operational purposes and meaning of the data are preserved and unaltered." When structural interoperability, or structured transport, is achieved, all the data is standardized to a particular format so it can be interpreted by multiple systems or devices. This data is organized in a particular order so the receiving system can automatically detect specific data fields. Data standards like FHIR and HL7

provide structural interoperability so records can be consistent, centralized and easy to move between systems.

6.6. AIR principles.

In order to promote improved technical interoperability, it is also advisable to make use of the FAIR principles. As previously presented, the acronym refers to Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability.

The principle of **Findability** requires data to be identified, described and registered or indexed in a clear and unequivocal manner. Data should be assigned a unique and persistent identifier; that the main characteristics of data are systematically specified, ideally using standard formats; and that these are stored or indexed in a public resource such as a data archive or institutional repository.

The principle of **Accessibility** requires that datasets should be accessible through a clearly defined access procedure, ideally by automated means. This entails the establishment of authentication and authorisation procedures for access as well as the implementation of automated data retrieval protocols where appropriate. Metadata should always be accessible even if the underlying data is not or no longer available.

The principle of **Interoperability** requires that data and metadata are conceptualised, expressed and structured using common, published standards. This entails drawing on standard technical and semantic data formats, variables, ontologies and the like. Moreover, such standards should themselves be made FAIR, meaning at the very least that they are published, traceable and accessible.

The principle of **Reusability** lies at the core of the FAIR Principles, in particular within the context of legal interoperability. It requires that characteristics of the data and their provenance should be described in detail according to domain-relevant community standards, with clear and accessible conditions for use. This entails providing and publishing accurate and relevant data descriptions, access and usage licences, the community standards which have been employed in the process as well as the associated provenance for each and every dataset.

6.7. Recommendations

- Encourage greater cooperation between Member States. Member States who share a common strategy shall be strongly encouraged to collaborate in order to avoid redundancy and minimize costs. This collaboration can take the form of common investment in expensive tools (e.g., terminology server), exchange of tenders, exchange of methodology, cross-validation of translations, training of experts and evaluation of pilots. In order to make this possible, a common understanding of the strategies chosen by all Member States is an essential prerequisite.
- Encourage greater cooperation between national authorities and standardisation bodies. Member States and the European Commission shall encourage standardisation bodies to enhance their strategic and operational cooperation. Furthermore, cooperation between standardisation organisations and competent national authorities in Member States shall be fostered.
- Enable the recommendation of standards and (harmonised) profiles based on selected Use Cases. Based on (selected) Use Cases, an organisation shall be in charge of a) the evidence-based selection of Use Cases b) the recommendation of standards and profiles for these selected Use Cases. The selection process for both Use Cases and recommendations shall be run jointly by domain experts and end users. Particular

consideration should be given to those Use Cases mentioned in articles 11 and 14 of the Directive 2011/24/EU on patients' rights in cross-border health care.

- Use purchasing power of public sector as an enabler for semantic and technical interoperability. The public sector, as a major purchaser of eHealth applications and systems, shall require vendors to use recommended standards, profiles and coding systems in public tenders.
- Foster data portability.
 - Data portability for healthcare providers. Vendors shall be required to implement an import/export function in a recommended standard based on a recommended data model in order to facilitate the re-hosting of medical data. This measure mitigates the risk of failure of the IT infrastructure, enables the re-hosting of medical data and avoids the lock-in of healthcare providers.
 - Data portability for patients. Vendors and healthcare providers shall be required to provide patients access to their data (in particular images, lab results, health records) in a recommended standard.
- Link and harmonise coding systems. Organisations responsible for the development and maintenance of coding systems as well as Member States and the European Commission shall work towards linking, harmonising and converging coding systems in healthcare.
- Facilitate access to existing standards and medical vocabularies. License conditions of existing standards and medical vocabularies are sometimes highly restrictive and may not be affordable for all business cases. In order to facilitate their adoption, mandatory semantic standards and medical vocabularies shall be provided by public authorities. The documentation of technical standards and, in particular, standards emerging from publicly funded projects shall be provided for free on the internet and, wherever applicable, be supported by one or more reference implementations that are preferably open source.
- Stimulate usability engineering for structured and encoded data. The limited usability of user interfaces for the entry of encoded and structured data turns out to be an additional burden for healthcare professionals. Member States and the European Commission shall stimulate research on the development and use of scalable interfaces for structured and encoded data.
- Consider incentivisation of healthcare providers. Providing medical records that can be semantically shared incurs costs for healthcare professionals. Member States should therefore identify and calculate the value proposition of healthcare providers with regard to interoperability and consider sustainable incentivisation schemes to encourage healthcare providers to provide data in an interoperable way and to invest in interoperable software.
- Make use of technological advances. With advances in cloud computing, especially hybrid cloud, it has become easier for organizations to move and secure data in a consistent way. Cloud environments provide opportunities for organizations to build data pipelines that standardize data to an industry-standard format like FHIR and provide secure access to people who need it, whether they are payers, providers or patients themselves.

7. Main benefits of enhanced interoperability

Mobile and ubiquitous access to medical information.

Semantic and technical interoperability enables access to, and correct interpretation of, medical information by different first responders and medical disciplines as well as in different countries, regions and nations. Furthermore, it ensures that, as patients access care from a variety of health care providers, there is a seamless flow of a patient's medical history.

Enhanced quality of care.

Semantic and technical interoperability assure a common understanding of medical information and subsequently lead to a reduction in medical and prescription errors. They also enhance the quality of care by enabling better and faster coordination between the different healthcare professionals and providers. This in turn improves continuity of care through enhanced communication of the patient's health status, performed procedures, family history and personal history.

Improved cost efficiency.

Semantic and technical interoperability provide the basis so that the right information can be available in the right way at the right time. This improves medical decision making while, at the same time, reduces risks and cost. In particular, it avoids duplicate, medically unnecessary (laboratory) tests and imaging procedures.

Enhanced choice for healthcare providers.

Interoperability of vendor systems enhances the choice for healthcare providers: if the solutions are interoperable, providers have more choice in buying what they need in a competitive market and at lower costs while, at the same, time vendors can introduce their products to more markets, thus reducing further development investment.

Faster emergency response

If emergency responders use common tools, vocabulary and processes, the response will be much faster. By improving interoperability, including coordination and communication, efforts can be better managed.

Better care coordination

With access to data, clinicians have an easier time accessing a patient's most important health information, which can lead to fewer repeat tests, prevent inadvertent treatment interactions and reduce miscommunications.

Higher performance

When data can be combined more easily, it can also be analysed more easily. Interoperability makes it possible for organizations to study data trends, past performance and make data-driven improvements in patient care and other areas.

Improved business and administrative processes

If the measures studied are implemented, it will be easier to map processes, analyse them, redesign them, acquire resources, communicate and review them. Administrative tasks would be simplified and synergies improved.

Increased patient safety and satisfaction

Improved interoperability will streamline processes; reduce wasteful spending, allowing money to be spent on improving services; and reduce planning times, allowing institutions to concentrate efforts on ensuring quality and security of coverage.

Better experiences

Data interoperability can reduce the amount of redundant administrative work both within and outside organizations, creating a more satisfying experiences both for employees and for those they serve.

8. Related projects, initiatives and instruments

- **Financial instruments.** The Commission will support, promote and monitor the implementation of the interoperability action plan, and the European interoperability framework in general, primarily through the ISA² programme. Planned actions may also in whole or in part be financed by other instruments, for example:
 - Horizon 2020 can support actions related to innovation in the public sector;
 - ‘Connecting Europe’ facility can support the deployment and use of key cross border mature digital services such as electronic identification, procurement and interoperable health services;
 - The European structural and investment funds can support actions related to digital growth through the development of ICT products and services and those related to strengthening the institutional capacity and efficiency of public administrations;

The structural reform support programme can support public administrations in the implementation of the national dimension of the European interoperability framework. **EOSCsecretariat.eu** delivers support to the EOSC Governance while working openly and inclusively with communities to co-create an all-encompassing European Open Science Cloud. Within our remit as the Coordination and Support Action for the EOSC, we address the need for the set-up of an operational framework supporting the overall Governance of the EOSC and engage with fully with EOSC-related projects.

- **FASTER** is an H2020 project that involves a consortium of research, social and technical partners and first responder organizations. FASTER addresses the challenges associated with the protection of first responders in hazardous environments, while at the same time enhancing their capabilities in terms of situational awareness and communication.
- **EGALURG** (POCTEFA EFA 305/19). European initiative targeted for investment in social and healthcare infrastructure that contributes to national, regional and local development and reduces healthcare inequalities. It is also closely aligned with the area of specific risk assessment and intervention and the development of systems for managing disasters.
- **Component "Health Information Exchange" (HIE):** Part of a country’s enterprise architecture that connects multiple applications and allows them to move data between one another using standards bundled together to provide implementation guidance for the software developers. This approach overcomes the quadratic cost problem. One characteristic of HIE is that it stores lists of terms and concepts mapping how these lists relate to each other across different applications. Standards make this mapping process easier. HIE receives data from each of the applications and keeps track of how they relate and will translate between the different applications in real time. This enables three or more applications to communicate through HIE as a central translator. Now, any new application that gets added only needs to be able to communicate with the HIE. And if an application changes only the HIE needs to be updated while all the other applications can still communicate. (National HIE, regional, local...).
- **WiFIS Interoperability Framework** (Work Flow for Health Institutions). The WiFIS interoperability framework allows the centres of the Integrated Public Use Healthcare System of Catalonia (SISCAT) to exchange information in a standardized way,

normalizing the processes and communications between the systems of primary, specialized or mental healthcare centres.

In order to carry out the standardization of processes and communications, Implementation Guides have been created which define the rules, information exchange models, messaging and terminology that must be used in order to carry out this standardization. All centres that follow the implementation guidelines, and therefore implement the WiFIS interoperability framework, will have the ability to connect to the interoperability platform defined in the iS3 project in order to exchange information with the other centres that use the same protocol. The main standards on which the WiFIS Interoperability Framework is based are HL7 V2.5 messaging (with some adoptions from version 2.7 and later), and SNOMED CT terminology to represent its content.

- **Data Use and Reciprocal Support Agreement (DURSA).** The DURSA builds upon the various legal requirements that participants are already subject to and describes the mutual responsibilities, obligations and expectations of all participants under the Agreement. All of these responsibilities, obligations and expectations create a framework for safe and secure health information exchange and are designed to promote trust among participants and protect the privacy, confidentiality and security of the health data that is shared.

The DURSA is a legally enforceable contract that represents a framework for broad-based information exchange among a set of trusted entities. The Agreement reflects a consensus among the state-level, federal and private entities who were involved in the development of the DURSA regarding the following issues:

- Multi-Party Agreement.
 - Participants Actively Engaged in Health Information Exchange.
 - Privacy and Security Obligations.
 - Requests for Information Based on a Permitted Purpose.
 - Duty to Respond.
 - Future Use of Data Received from Another Participant.
 - Respective Duties of Submitting and Receiving Participants.
 - Autonomy Principle for Access.
 - Use of Authorizations to Support Requests for Data.
 - Data Privacy and Security.
 - Mandatory Non-Binding Dispute Resolution.
 - Allocation of Liability Risk.
- **eHealth Standards and Profiles in Action for Europe and Beyond (eStandards)** is a proposed coordination and support action to strengthen the standards and interoperability pillar of DAE2020, by alignment and wide adoption of standards in eHealth market for products and services, advance global competitiveness of the eHealth industry, and support seamless, trusted, and safer health care in our society.

Recognizing that this is a time for action, CEN/TC251, HL7, IHE, leading Standards and Profile Development Organizations (SDOs), join forces to create an active evidence-driven roadmap to drive eHealth interoperability in Europe and beyond. In their quest for alignment and consensus to advance timely informed care in quality and safety, SDOs have partnered with enablers and implementers (OFFIS, EuroRec, RAMIT, MEDIQ), end users (HOPE), Member States, Regions, and Competence Centres supporting large scale

eHealth Deployments (Region of Lombardy (IT), NICTIZ (NL), SPMSS(PT)), and the industry (COCIR).

- **EUREGIO II.** Solutions for improving health care cooperation in border regions. The general objective of the EUREGIO II project was to stimulate and promote cross-border cooperation in healthcare in border regions by fostering the usability of various existing instruments and methods. The project focused mostly on the effective use of structural funds, improvement in the provision of healthcare services, extension of cross-border healthcare provision, quality development, costs savings and better use of resources.

Three deliverables were produced by the partners involved:

- Handbook on the effective use of INTERREG funding in cross-border healthcare.
- Guideline for the use of Health Technology Assessment (HTA) in border settings.
- Legal Report concerning liability and data protection issues in cross-border cooperation.

The three-year project EUREGIO II ran from 2008 to 2011 and was a successor of the project "Evaluation of cross border activities in the European Union" (EUREGIO, 2004-2007), in which HOPE was also involved, and complementary to the project "Health investments in Structural Funds 2000-2006: learning lessons to inform regions in the 2007-2013 period" (EUREGIO III). All of these projects have received funding under the Public Health Programme of the European Union.

- **NATO Federated Interoperability.** Although this initiative is motivated by the improvement of interoperability in the field of defence, we believe that it can be useful as a reference, since it dedicates a significant effort to improving cooperation between different actors; to the elaboration of doctrinal documents that unify principles and processes; and to the achievement of capabilities that increase effectiveness and the achievement of objectives. This can be transferred to the field of emergencies in which Valkyries participates, as here, too, collaboration between countries with different objective resources, resources and processes can be observed.

This initiative considers interoperability as *"the ability to act together coherently, effectively and efficiently to achieve Allied objectives"*. They see federated interoperability as a collective effort shared between Alliance and Partner Nations and other organizations. The 'Interoperability Continuum' enables federated interoperability by linking three major HQ SACT interoperability events; the Coalition Warrior Interoperability Exercise (CWIX), The Think-Tank for Information Decision and Execution (TIDE) Sprint, and the TIDE Hackathon. Its purpose is to ensure that the C2 capabilities can exchange operational information in the right format, to the right person at the right time so that NATO commanders and decision makers have the situational awareness needed to make good decisions.

- **NATO Federated Mission Networking (FMN).** This initiative aims, like the previous one, at improving interoperability in the field of defence and military operations. The concept developed as "Federated Mission Networking", provides overall guidance for achieving the capability to deploy "Federated Mission Networks" that enable the effective exchange of information between NATO, NATO Nations and/or non-NATO entities engaged in operations, supporting Command and Control as well as decision-making.

The new FMN capability will affect the way operations are planned and executed. It has a particular impact on the interoperability of forces and requires the execution of numerous actions that go beyond the CIS environment and cover different fields such

as organisation, doctrine, capability planning, definition and procurement of different types of assets, training, planning and execution of operations, operational procedures and security, among others.

The federation of networks establishes not only the technical solution but also the security solution, validation, work processes, training... the objective is to interconnect services, not just networks. It also includes the prior actions of defining operational processes, training, doctrinal adaptations... in such a way as to reduce the training and certification times of the forces, the technical and operational costs, and the magnitude of the tasks associated with creating Mission Networks for a specific operation.

Looking at the main references on FMN, the following can be detailed. 'Federated' is a key contribution to the Connected Forces Initiative (CFI), helping Allied and Partner forces to better communicate, train and operate together. 'Mission' enables a rapid instantiation of mission networks by federating NATO organizations, NATO Nations and Mission Partner capabilities, thereby enhancing interoperability and information sharing. 'Networking' is a governed conceptual framework consisting of people, processes and technology to plan, prepare, establish, use and terminate mission networks in support of federated operations.

Furthermore, FMN is a capability aiming to support C2 and decision-making in future operations through improved information-sharing. It provides the agility, flexibility and scalability needed to manage the emerging requirements of any mission environment in future NATO operations. FMN is based on principles that include cost effectiveness and maximum reuse of existing standards and capabilities. It consists of three elements: Federated Mission Networking Governance, Federated Mission Networking Framework and Mission Networks.

Promoting planning guidelines or tools, making them standard and practical, can greatly enhance coalition interoperability. This would improve readiness and effectiveness, exploiting a strategic, operational and tactical advantage. While it is true that not all elements surrounding military operations can be covered or homogenised, for a multitude of reasons, C2 can be facilitated by following similar principles and processes. NATO's C3 doctrine and taxonomy contribute greatly to this.

- **European Network for Research Ethics Committees (EUREC).** Network that brings together already existing national Research Ethics Committees (RECs) associations, networks or comparable initiatives on the European level.
- **European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI).** Establishes an operable platform of actors in the fields of research ethics and research integrity.
- **Mapping Normative Frameworks for Ethics and Integrity of Research (EnTIRE).** The aim is to create a platform that makes the normative framework governing Research Ethics and Research Integrity (RE+RI) easily accessible, supports application in research and evaluation.
- **Shaping the ethical dimensions of smart information systems (SIS), a European perspective (SHERPA).** Investigate, analyse and synthesise the ways in which smart information systems impact ethics and human rights issues.

- **Responsible Open Science in Europe (ROSiE)**. Provide an analysis and develop practical tools aimed at ensuring ethics and research integrity in open science and citizen science.

9. Use Cases Lessons Learned

Through the examination of practical Use Cases developed in the context of the Valkyries project, this section seeks to distill valuable lessons learned that can inform future endeavors to enhance interoperability in cross-border emergency situations and discusses the conclusions that stakeholders may have reached through these Use Cases. Specific information about the Use Cases and the implementation of the solutions proposed can be found in the Report of each specific Use Case. As of the time of writing this report, the final Use Case (UC#4 Norw.-Den.-Sweden) has not been performed yet, but the previous three Use Cases offer enough information to grant arriving to these conclusions with significant certainty.

Interoperability is essential for effective emergency response and patient care in cross-border disasters. However, achieving seamless interoperability poses numerous challenges, as we have explored in this deliverable, considering the risks presented from different perspectives, which we have summarized in nine specific risks from which we can focus on the lessons learned from testing interoperability systems in various practical Use Cases to better understand the complexities and potential solutions.

- **Disjointed Coordination**

One of the significant challenges identified is disjointed coordination among healthcare organizations during emergency situations. Use Cases have shown that pre-planning and establishing and maintaining relationships are essential for improving coordination. Conclusions may have been reached regarding the need for dedicated communication channels and integrated technologies, especially when rapid response is critical. The integration of technologies and the establishment of clear communication protocols could be seen as critical conclusions from these tests.

One key lesson learned is the necessity of pre-established protocols and agreements between neighboring regions or countries. These agreements should outline communication channels, the sharing of resources, and the deployment of specialized teams, ensuring a coordinated effort.

Another crucial lesson is the value of cross-border training and familiarity among first responders. Effective communication and collaboration require an understanding of each agency's capabilities, resources, and protocols.

A clear command structure is vital in any emergency response, especially in cross-border situations. It helps prevent confusion and ensures that decision-making processes are streamlined.

Effective communication is at the heart of successful coordination. In cross-border situations, language barriers and cultural differences can hinder communication and cooperation. First responders should receive training in language skills and cultural sensitivity to overcome these obstacles and build trust among teams.

Cross-border emergency situations may overwhelm local resources. To address this, lessons learned should emphasize the importance of resource sharing and mutual aid agreements.

- **Lack of Standardization**

Lack of standardization in healthcare systems hampers interoperability efforts. Practical testing revealed the importance of implementing standards and specifications according to predefined plans and practical guidelines. The necessity of monitoring compliance with these standards and the value of managing change with appropriate procedures became apparent in the development of the Use Cases. The practical Use Cases may

have also underscored the significance of documenting standards and specifications in open catalogues using standardized descriptions, promoting transparency and ease of integration.

Effective communication is paramount in any emergency response. Standardized communication protocols, such as radio frequencies and codes, should be established and agreed upon in advance.

Standardizing equipment is crucial to avoid compatibility issues during a cross-border response. Responding agencies should adopt equipment and technologies that are interoperable and can be readily used by all teams involved. This ensures that resources can be pooled efficiently, reducing duplication and enhancing the overall response capacity.

A unified and standardized incident command system is vital for cross-border emergency responses. A single command structure with clearly defined roles and responsibilities streamlines decision-making and eliminates confusion. Lessons learned should emphasize the need for adopting and practicing a common incident command system.

Cross-border responses often involve navigating different regulatory frameworks. Lessons learned should underscore the importance of aligning regulations and policies across borders where possible, especially in critical areas like hazardous materials handling and environmental protection. This can expedite response efforts and minimize bureaucratic hurdles.

- **Limited Budgets**

Financial constraints often hinder investments in interoperability. Many healthcare organizations struggle to allocate the necessary resources. Use Cases have led to conclusions about the need for creative solutions, such as collaborative partnerships and shared resource pools. While prioritizing investments to ensure that interoperability projects are sustainable and that they deliver tangible benefits in emergency situations is important, we must take into account the tangible reality of a lack of direct control over the financial aspect by the first responders, and the need to work within realistic limitations to come up with solutions.

One of the primary lessons from Use Cases is the need for resource prioritization. When budgets are limited, responders must allocate resources strategically based on critical needs.

Use Cases emphasized the importance of mutual aid agreements between neighboring regions or countries. These agreements can provide a framework for sharing resources and personnel during emergencies.

Community engagement and volunteer participation can be invaluable in supplementing limited budgets. Use Cases highlight the need for first responders to work closely with local communities, encouraging citizen involvement in preparedness and response efforts. This can include training volunteers in disaster response roles and mobilizing community resources when budgets are constrained.

Budget limitations can stimulate creativity and the development of innovative solutions. Lessons learned stress the importance of embracing technology and creative problem-solving to optimize resource utilization. For instance, using drones for wildfire surveillance or developing low-cost communication systems can enhance response capabilities even on limited budgets.

Use Cases can serve as a catalyst for advocating for adequate funding for emergency response. Lessons learned should underscore the importance of adequately funding emergency services to ensure they have the resources they need to effectively protect lives and property during cross-border emergencies.

- **Diverse Technology Needs**

Diverse technology needs in healthcare stem from varying rules and regulations across countries and organizations. Customized data and processes further complicate interoperability efforts. Conclusions drawn from practical Use Cases revolve around the necessity of creating adaptable and flexible interoperability solutions capable of accommodating diverse technology needs without compromising data integrity or security. Stakeholders have recognized the importance of scalability and adaptability in the design of interoperability frameworks.

One key lesson from Use Cases is the importance of establishing interoperability standards for communication and data sharing. Responders from different regions may use varying communication systems and software.

Diverse technology needs highlight the need for comprehensive training and familiarity among first responders. Practical exercises, such as joint training sessions and cross-border drills, can help responders become proficient in using a range of technologies.

Cross-border response teams must be prepared to share technology resources and establish redundancy plans. Use Cases underscore the importance of having backup systems and equipment available in case of technology failures.

Use Cases highlight the value of public-private partnerships in leveraging technology resources. Collaboration with technology companies and private sector organizations can provide access to advanced tools and expertise that may not be readily available within the public sector. These partnerships can help bridge technology gaps during cross-border emergencies.

The evolving nature of technology requires first responders to embrace continuous improvement and adaptability. Lessons learned emphasize the need for regular technology assessments and updates to ensure that response capabilities remain effective in the face of rapidly changing threats. Cross-border collaboration should also be adaptable to incorporate emerging technologies.

- **Legacy Systems**

Healthcare organizations with legacy systems face the dual challenge of modernization and meeting interoperability requirements. Though this particular enterprise falls outside of the possible scope of the project, practical testing has led to conclusions suggesting that phased approaches to system modernization are often more practical than complete overhauls. Bridging solutions and middleware may have been identified as key components in enabling data exchange between legacy and modern systems.

One key lesson from Use Cases is the importance of addressing legacy system compatibility and integration challenges. Responders must invest in bridging the gap between legacy systems and modern technologies to facilitate communication and data sharing.

Use Cases underscore the need for standardization and the development of common protocols when dealing with legacy systems. Creating standardized data formats and communication protocols can help ensure that information can be exchanged between agencies with different technologies.

Interagency training is crucial when dealing with legacy systems. Responders should be trained to work with diverse technologies and be familiar with the strengths and limitations of legacy systems. Practical exercises can help first responders become proficient in using both legacy and modern technologies to ensure effective communication during cross-border emergencies.

Managing legacy systems requires a strategy for incremental upgrades and modernization. Lessons learned stress the importance of budgeting for these upgrades to gradually replace or enhance outdated technologies.

When transitioning from legacy systems, preserving critical data and ensuring data migration is essential. Use Cases emphasize the need for backup and data preservation plans to avoid loss of critical information during technology transitions.

- **Security**

Balancing the need for information accessibility with the imperative to secure sensitive data and protect patient privacy is a formidable challenge. Conclusions drawn from practical Use Cases emphasize the critical nature of robust security measures. Continuous monitoring and audit trails have been recognized as essential components of these measures. The Use Cases have also highlighted the need for rigorous implementation of encryption, access controls, and authentication mechanisms to safeguard patient information during interoperable data exchanges.

One primary lesson from Use Cases is the need for robust security preparedness. Responders must be trained to recognize and respond to security threats effectively.

Use Cases underscore the importance of secure communication protocols and encryption in cross-border emergency response. Responders should use technologies that safeguard sensitive information from interception or manipulation.

Balancing the need for information sharing with security concerns is crucial. Lessons learned stress the importance of information classification and the need to limit access to sensitive data. Responders should have clear guidelines on what information can be shared with whom during cross-border emergencies, ensuring that critical information reaches the right parties while protecting sensitive data.

Use Cases highlight the value of public-private partnerships in enhancing cybersecurity capabilities.

Security risks evolve over time, necessitating continual evaluation and adaptation of security measures. Lessons learned emphasize the importance of regularly reviewing and updating cybersecurity protocols to address emerging threats and vulnerabilities.

- **Consent**

Respecting patient consent is paramount in healthcare interoperability. Practical testing has led to conclusions emphasizing the importance of integrating consent management into interoperability systems. Clear policies and procedures for data sharing and consent tracking should be developed in order to create a system that rises to the standards set regarding Data Protection. Technological solutions that streamline the consent process while maintaining transparency have been identified as valuable outcomes of these Use Cases.

One fundamental lesson from Use Cases is the importance of establishing clear protocols for obtaining consent. Cross-border emergency response plans should include guidelines on when, how, and from whom consent should be sought. This clarity can help responders navigate consent-related challenges more effectively.

Cross-cultural understanding and sensitivity are essential when dealing with consent risks. Practical exercises should incorporate cultural competency training for responders to ensure they respect local customs and traditions when seeking consent. This fosters trust and cooperation with affected communities.

To address legal consent risks, lessons learned emphasize the importance of harmonizing legal frameworks between neighboring regions. Governments should collaborate to establish agreements and mechanisms that align consent requirements, reducing the potential for legal conflicts in cross-border emergency situations.

Use Cases highlight the value of community engagement in obtaining consent. Responders should actively involve local communities in the decision-making process and ensure that their voices are heard. Engaging community leaders and influencers can help build trust and facilitate cooperation.

Obtaining informed consent is critical. Lessons learned stress the importance of transparent communication with affected communities. Responders should provide clear information about the situation, risks, and response efforts, allowing individuals to make informed decisions regarding their consent.

- **Professional Burdens**

Introducing new tools for recordkeeping can burden healthcare professionals who need to learn and adapt to them. Conclusions drawn from practical Use Cases highlight the significance of user-friendly interfaces and comprehensive training programs. Stakeholders have recognized the need for substantial investments in training and user support to minimize the impact on professionals' workloads. Additionally, Use Cases have generated insights into optimizing the integration of new tools into existing workflows.

- **Heterogeneous Landscape of Healthcare Systems in Europe**

Europe's healthcare landscape is highly heterogeneous due to historical and treaty-defined reasons. Practical testing has led to conclusions that underscore the necessity of interoperability solutions accounting for this diversity. Flexible data exchange frameworks capable of adapting to varying healthcare systems and regulatory environments have been recognized as a key outcome. Conclusions have also emphasized the importance of cross-border collaboration and standardization efforts to bridge gaps in interoperability within the European healthcare context.

In conclusion, the lessons learned from practical testing of interoperability systems in healthcare have provided valuable insights into addressing the identified risks. These lessons have informed stakeholders of the crucial aspects of pre-planning, standardization, resource allocation, adaptability, phased modernization, robust security measures, patient consent management, user-friendly interfaces, and accommodating heterogeneous landscapes. The conclusions drawn from these Use Cases serve as a foundation for enhancing interoperability in healthcare systems, ultimately improving emergency response and patient care while addressing the unique challenges posed by different contexts and regions. Further research and collaboration can build upon these lessons to continue advancing healthcare interoperability in the face of emergent challenges.

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11. Annex B – Regulation, decisions and communiqués

ANNEX to the COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION adopting the fourth revision of the work programme implementing the programme on interoperability solutions and common frameworks for European public administrations, business and citizens (the ISA² programme) and the breakdown of corresponding budgetary expenditure for 2020.

COM(2010) 744 final, Annex 1.

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Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation).

12. Annex C – Glossary

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CCO	Creative Commons No Rights Reserved
CDA	Clinical Document Architecture
CDC	Centres for Disease Control and Prevention
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
COCIR	Coordination Committee of the Radiological, Electromedical and Healthcare IT Industry
COM	Communiqué
CPT	Current Procedural Terminology
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DURSA	Data Use and Reciprocal Support Agreement
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EIRA	European Interoperability Architecture
EIS	European Interoperability Strategy
EMPI	Enterprise Master Patient Index
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FMN	Federated Mission Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
HIE	Health Information Exchange
HIMSS	Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society
HL7	Health Level Seven
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IHE	Integrating Healthcare Enterprise
IMIA	International Medical Informatics Association
ISA	Interoperability Solutions for European Public Administrations
IT	Information Technology

Acronym	Description
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
MOU	Memorandum of understanding
MRN	Medical Record Number
NIF	National Interoperability Framework
NIFO	National Interoperability Framework Observatory
NPI	National Provider Identifier
OID	Object Identifier
PDDL	Public Domain Dedication and Licence
SDO	Standard Developing Organisation
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNOMED	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine
SQL	Structured Query Language
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Table 1 - Glossary